

ANALYZING TRANSLATION OUTPUT AND PREFERENCES: A BASIS FOR THE DESIGN OF TRANSLATION SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the preferences for types of translation used in selected lines from the historical film Heneral Luna. Specifically, the researchers translated 50 selected lines from the film into the target language using the four translation types: word-for-word, grammatical, idiomatic, and communicative. The respondents were composed of 35 third-year English major students, 25 third-year Filipino major students, and 22 language teachers from the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. The researchers employed a descriptive-developmental research method and utilized survey-type questionnaires as the primary tool for data collection. After gathering and analyzing the responses, the findings revealed that among the four types of translation, word-for-word and idiomatic translations emerged as the most preferred across all respondent groups. English and Filipino major students tended to favor the word-for-word approach for its directness and familiarity, while language teachers preferred idiomatic translation for its ability to convey meaning naturally and fluently in the target language. Based on the results, the researchers developed a supplementary material that highlights the challenges in translation and provided further discussion on the different translation techniques used in study. This material used as instructional support to enhance students' understanding and competence in translation-related courses. The findings suggested the need to balance literal and idiomatic translation strategies in educational settings to address learners' preferences and improved overall translation quality. These insights could help refine teaching and learning of translation in both theoretical and practical contexts.

Keywords: *Translation, Preferences, Word for word Translation, Grammatical Translation, Idiomatic Translation and Communicative Translation*

INTRODUCTION

The translation of films and audiovisual texts has been a challenging endeavor, as many audiovisual translations struggle to balance linguistic fidelity with the constraints of time, space, and audience comprehension, leading to viewer dissatisfaction, misinterpretation, and the loss of important cultural references. As stated by Sonia Colina (2015), translation can be understood as an activity and a result, involving the transfer of meaning from a source language to a target language.

According to Elsevier (2015) highlights that translation plays a significant role in second language acquisition, influencing vocabulary learning and comprehension processes. Studies have highlighted how audience preferences and expectations vary, yet these are not always considered in translation processes, resulting in outputs that may be technically correct but culturally disconnected. The need for translation is evident in mass media commodities such as films, which have been exported and imported by nations, and both learners and educators have a positive attitude toward the use of movies, as well-selected materials encourage language learning by providing vocabulary, phrases, and colloquial expressions according to Yaseen and Shakir (2015), movies are effective tools for language learning as they expose students to authentic vocabulary, expressions, and contextual language use, which enhances comprehension and supports positive learning attitudes. Students stated that English subtitled movies motivate and encourage them to learn the English language and help them learn new vocabulary.

Despite the increasing demand for high-quality translations, there are persistent challenges in achieving linguistic and cultural accuracy, and 40% of consumers find translation errors a barrier to comprehension. According to Cuc (2017), students commonly commit errors in translation involving vocabulary, grammar, and sentence structure, which affect the clarity and meaning of the translated text. These errors often result from limited language proficiency and lack of translation training, according to Tan (2015), English-as-a-Foreign-Language (EFL) learners with lower levels of English competence tend to rely on basic or inappropriate translation strategies, which can lead to repeated errors in their translations due to gaps in vocabulary knowledge and linguistic control. This suggests that a lack of strong language skills and targeted translation training contributes to errors in the translation process. The lack of standardized translation strategies has led to inconsistencies in film and media, affecting how historical narratives are perceived by non-Filipino audiences. Translation is an essential skill for BSED English majors, as it bridges linguistic and cultural gaps, and translation courses can bridge the gap between theory and practice, enabling pre-service teachers to navigate between English and Filipino or other regional languages. However, many students in this program struggle with translation due to insufficient formal training, limited exposure to structured and practical translation exercises, and a lack of awareness or appreciation for the role of translation in language instruction.

Thus, this study sought to evaluate translation output and audience preferences as a foundation for developing supplementary materials that would enhance translation quality in historical films. By addressing translation inconsistencies and audience reception, the research aimed to contribute to translation studies and media localization efforts. Developing strong translation competence among BSED English majors was deemed crucial, as it influenced their ability to teach English effectively, and this study contributed to the advancement of language education by providing future teachers with essential tools.

Research Questions

This study aimed to analyze translation output and preferences. The findings served as a foundation for designing and developing supplementary materials that enhanced translation skills, promoted a deeper appreciation for its value, and addressed misconceptions.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the translation output of the film *Heneral Luna* in terms of:
 - 1.1 Word for word;
 - 1.2 Grammatical;
 - 1.3 Idiomatic;
 - 1.4 Communicative?
2. What are the participant's preferences grouped into:
 - 2.1 English Major Students;
 - 2.2 Filipino Major Students;
 - 2.3 Language Teachers?
3. What instructional materials can be designed based on the results of the study?

Research Locale

This study was conducted at the CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc., an educational institution known for providing diverse learning opportunities at various academic levels. The school was recognized for its commitment to academic excellence and creating a supportive learning environment. Its curriculum was designed to enhance students' critical thinking and communication abilities.

The CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc., was chosen as the research locale as it is one of the schools in Sariaya that exhibiting significantly large population of language educators major and offers Translation subject making it particularly suitable in this study that aimed to analyze translation output and preferences.

METHODOLOGY

This section discussed the research methods, research design, research locale, research population and sample, research instrument, data gathering procedures, and statistical treatment of data. The methods described ensure the reliability and validity of the research findings.

Research Design

The researchers utilized descriptive- developmental research. This approach helped to measure and analyze translation output and preferences. The descriptive approach provided a detailed description of the current state of these factors, capturing how translators perceived their roles, the value placed on translation in different contexts, and the competencies they possessed. Developmental research in analyzing translation output and preferences in translation aimed at creating a basis for the development of supplementary material focused on identifying gaps in existing resources and tools used for translation.

As defined by Singh (2023), descriptive research is a methodological approach that seeks to depict the characteristics of a phenomenon or subject under investigation. In scientific inquiry, it served as a foundational tool for researchers aiming to observe, record, and analyze the intricate details of a particular topic. This method provided a rich and detailed account that aids in understanding, categorizing, and interpreting the subject matter. Developmental research design refers to a systematic approach aimed at creating, testing, and refining educational programs, products, or interventions to address specific needs or problems. It involved the iterative process of designing a prototype or model, testing it in real- world settings, gathering feedback, and refining it to improve its effectiveness and applicability. The primary goal of developmental research design was to develop practical solutions or tools that are directly relevant to the field of study, often in areas like education, technology, and social programs. The design was continuously improved based on evaluations and feedback to ensure the final product meets the intended objectives (DeMarco 2023).

The descriptive- developmental research design was appropriate for this study because it focused on describing characteristics of a population or situation, with developmental research, which investigated changes and patterns over a period. This study aimed to measure the problem and develop a material in perception, competence and valuing in translations. Since it was a descriptive- developmental, it focused on describing a phenomenon while also tracking its changes and developing the appropriate supplementary material to improve and understand the translation process.

Research Population

The respondents of the study were selected from CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications, Inc. CSTC was the only school in Sariaya to exhibit a large population of language educators.

Furthermore, in choosing the respondents, purposive sampling was employed as sampling method for the study. Purposive sampling is a non- probability sampling technique commonly used in quantitative research. In this method, the researchers intentionally selected individuals or groups based on the qualities they possessed, particularly their knowledge, experience, or relevance to the research question. This approach ensured that the data gathered was rich, relevant, and deeply informative. According to Suri (2015), purposive sampling involved selecting “information- rich cases” for in- depth study, where participants were chosen because they could provide insight into the phenomenon being studied.

Research Instrument

The chosen film entitled "Heneral Luna" was carefully examined by the researcher. Thus, the Filipino translation of the film Heneral Luna was used by the researcher to translate the selected lines in other types of translation. Fifty (50) lines from the film were marked for determining the preferences of the types of translation using word for word, grammatical, idiomatic and interpretive translation. As part of this study, the researchers developed a checklist instrument designed to evaluate the translation preferences of respondents. This checklist presented selected dialogues from the historical film Heneral Luna, each rendered in four different English translations, corresponding to specific translation techniques, Word- for- Word, Grammatical, Idiomatic, and Communicative translations. The primary task of the respondents was to review each original Filipino line alongside its translated versions and indicate which translation they prefer. By selecting their most preferred version for each dialogue, respondents indirectly reveal their preferences regarding the applied translation techniques.

Data Gathering Procedures

To commence the study, the researchers first obtained the appropriate permissions from the administration and ethics review board of CSTC College of Sciences, Technology, and Communications Inc. A formal request letter was submitted to the Research Office and relevant school authorities to obtain approval for conducting the study among third year English and Filipino majors as well as language teachers. Once permission was granted, the researchers coordinated with the relevant English teachers and school administrators to schedule the administration of the translation task.

Upon approval, the researchers conducted a survey to the respondents by distributing the questionnaire and the given questionnaire answered by the respondents. The questionnaire was validated and was administered in- person. After the total return of the questionnaire, the data were collected and classified. The results of the study were identified as the proofs of the research study. All data collected were stored securely and confidentially. Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the study process. A confidentiality agreement was placed to protect the anonymity of participants. All data handling complied with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Data were anonymize to protect the identities of participants. All citations followed APA style, with a comprehensive reference

section included in the final report. Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical methods, and were presented clear and concisely.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following were the statistical treatments that the researchers used to analyze and statistically treat the data collected.

The Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) was used to analyze the data collected on students' preferences. The WAM was calculated by summing the products of each value and its corresponding weight, then dividing the total by the sum of the weights. This statistical measure provided a more accurate representation of the central tendency by accounting for the varying significance of different data points (Pounis 2019)

The formula of WAM

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n w_i}$$

Where:

W = weighted average

n = number of terms to be averaged

w = weights applied to x values

X- data value

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings obtained from the data gathered with the research instrument. The results are presented and interpreted in the form of tables to better understand thereaders regarding the implications and significance of the information gathered. The discussion of these results forms the foundation for developing a gender-responsive policy for the integration of AI in private schools, as well as for suggesting seminars.

Part I. Translation Output of the Film Heneral Luna

Table 1 Translation Output of the Film Heneral Luna

Descriptors	Frequency	Percentage
Word for word	1,199	29.24
Grammatical	974	23.76
Idiomatic	1065	25.98
Communicative	862	21.02
Total	4100	100

Table 1 presents the distribution of translation techniques based on the percentage of preferences among respondents. According to the data, word- for- word translation emerge as the most preferred technique, receiving 1,199 responses, which accounted for 29.24% of the total. This result indicates a strong inclination among participants toward translating texts in a literal manner, where each word in the source language is directly replaced with its counterpart in the target language. This technique, though often criticized for its lack of contextual adaptation, is appreciated for its simplicity and fidelity to the original structure and vocabulary. Closely following was the idiomatic translation technique, garnering 1,065 responses or 25.9%. This approach focuses on producing translations that sound natural, fluent, and culturally familiar to the target audience. Idiomatic translation prioritizes meaning over form, allowing translators to convey the intended message more effectively by adapting expressions and phrases to suit the linguistic norms of the target language. The third most preferred technique, according to the survey, is grammatical translation, which accounted for 974 responses or 23.76%. This method emphasizes the importance of syntactic correctness and structural alignment between the source and target texts. Finally, the communicative translation technique receives the fewest responses, totaling 862 or 21.02%. This method focuses on conveying the overall meaning and intent of the source text in a way that is easily understood by the target audience. It emphasizes reader response and functional clarity, often involving adjustments to suit cultural and contextual expectations to be average.

The findings clearly demonstrates that word- for- word translation is the most favored technique among CSTC teachers and students. This preference may have stem from a traditional approach to language learning and translation, where literal equivalence is often equated with accuracy. The results align with the findings of Karam & Smith (2020), who observes that word- for- word translation is frequently employed as the default strategy in domains like film subtitling, due to its straightforward nature and reduced cognitive load for translators. Their study highlights how such a method streamlines the translation process, especially when working under tight deadlines or limited linguistic flexibility.

Table 2 English Major Preference Translation Output

Descriptors	Frequency	Percentage
Word for word	621	35.49
Grammatical	490	28.00
Idiomatic	389	22.23
Communicative	250	14.29
Total	1750	100

Note. The respondents are 35 English Major students.

Table 2 presents the distribution of translation techniques preferred by English Major students, as reflected in the collected data. The results indicates that the most preferred technique was word- for- word translation, which receives 621 responses, accounting for 35.49% of the total. This significant percentage suggests that a large portion of English Major students prioritizes literal accuracy and direct lexical equivalence

when translating from one language to another. Word- for- word translation involved a close, almost mechanical rendering of each term in the source language into its direct counterpart in the target language. This approach is typically valued for its clarity and consistency, particularly in academic contexts where fidelity to the original text is often emphasized. The second most preferred technique is grammatical translation, with 490 responses or 28%. This indicated that a substantial number of students value not only lexical equivalence but also the syntactic structure and grammatical rules of both languages involved. Grammatical translation focuses on preserving sentence construction and proper usage, suggesting that these students are attentive to the rules of grammar and linguistic formality in their translation work. Their preference reflects an effort to produce translations that are not only accurate in content but also correct in form, which is essential in academic writing and formal communication. Idiomatic translation, with 389 responses or 22.23%, ranked third among the preferred techniques. This method allows for greater flexibility and creativity, enabling translators to express ideas in a way that sounds more natural and fluent in the target language.

The choice of this technique by a considerable portion of the respondents demonstrates a recognition of the importance of cultural and linguistic appropriateness, especially when translating informal, conversational, or literal. However, its lower ranking compared to word- for- word and grammatical translations may suggest that many students are still hesitant to diverge too far from the original texts. perhaps due to concerns about misinterpretation or loss of meaning. Finally, communicative translation receives the least number of responses— 250 or 14.29%. This technique prioritizes delivering the intended meaning and effect of the original message to the target audience, even if it requires substantial restructuring or adaptation of the text. The relatively lower preference for this method implies that fewer students are comfortable with taking such liberties in translation.

In summary, the data explicitly shows that the majority of English Major students preferred word- for- word translation over other techniques, highlighting a tendency toward literalism and precision in their translation practices. This finding aligns with the study of Gupta et al. (2019), who noted that word- for- word translation is often favored by novice and student translators because of its perceived accuracy, transparency, and simplicity. According to their research, such a method reduced ambiguity and helps ensure that the original meaning is preserved with minimal alteration, especially in educational settings where the primary goal is comprehension and linguistic

Table 3 Filipino Major Preference Translation Output

Descriptors	Frequency	Percentage
Word for word	438	36.87
Grammatical	261	21.97
Idiomatic	291	24.49
Communicative	198	16.67
Total	1188	100

Note. The respondents are 25 Filipino Major students.

Table 3 presents the percentage of translation techniques preferred by Filipino Major students, providing insight into their translation practices and priorities.

According to the results, the most preferred technique is word-for-word translation, which receives 438 responses, representing 36.87% of the total. This significant preference suggests that Filipino Major students prioritize accuracy and lexical fidelity between the source and target languages. By translating each word exactly as it appears in the original text, these students likely aimed to preserve the literal meaning, maintain clarity, and avoid misinterpretation. The second most preferred technique is idiomatic translation, with 291 responses or 24.49%. This method involves adapting expressions to sound more natural, fluent, and culturally appropriate in the target language, even if that means straying from the literal words of the source text. The considerable percentage of respondents selecting this method indicates an awareness among Filipino Major students of the need for cultural and contextual sensitivity in translation. Idiomatic translation often enhances reader engagement and comprehension, making it particularly useful in literary or creative translations.

Grammatical translation followed as the third most preferred responses or 21.97%. This approach emphasizes structural and syntactic accuracy, ensuring that the translated text conforms to the grammatical rules of the target language while maintaining the structure of the original. Students who prefer this technique may be particularly mindful of producing well-formed sentences that are both linguistically correct and faithful to the original text. Lastly, communicative translation is the least preferred technique, with 198 responses or 16.67%. Communicative translation aims to convey the intended message of the source text in a manner that is easily understood and contextually appropriate for the target audience. It often involves significant adaptation of the original language, including rewording and cultural localization. The relatively low preference for this technique suggests that fewer Filipino Major students are comfortable with the degree of interpretation and flexibility it requires.

Overall, the data explicitly showed that word-for-word translation was the most preferred technique among Filipino Major students. This preference highlighted a general inclination toward literal accuracy and straightforward translation processes, where minimal interpretation was involved. These findings were consistent with the study conducted by Gupta et al. (2019), who observed that word-for-word translation was often favored by students and beginner translators for its simplicity, transparency, and perceived precision. According to their research, this method was commonly used in academic and instructional contexts, where the goal was to retain the original meaning without adding subjective interpretation or ambiguity.

Table 4 Language Teachers Preference Translation Output

Descriptors	Frequency	Percentage
Word for word	140	10.16
Grammatical	223	16.18
Idiomatic	385	27.94

Communicative	630	45.72
Total	1378	100

Note. The respondents are 22 Language teachers.

Table 4 presents the percentage of translation techniques preferred by language teachers, offering valuable insights into the strategies they find most effective for educational and practical translation contexts. The data reveal that the most preferred technique among respondents is communicative translation, which received 630 responses, accounting for 45.72% of the total. This significant preference indicates that language teachers prioritize the clear and effective communication of meaning, adapting the original text as needed to suit the cultural and linguistic norms of the target audience. Communicative translation placed greater emphasis on the reader's understanding and context-specific relevance than on strict literal equivalence, making it a suitable method for educational, professional, and real-world communicative settings. Teachers favored this approach because it ensures that translated content is both accessible and preferred technique, with 261 meaningful, particularly in language teaching, where comprehension and context were critical. The second most preferred technique was idiomatic translation, with 385 responses or 27.94%. This method aims to render the translation in a way that sounds natural and familiar to native speakers of the target language. Idiomatic translation allows flexibility in phrasing and expression to capture the spirit and tone of the original text. The notable percentage of teachers favoring this approach suggests a recognition of the importance of fluency and reader engagement in translation. It also reflects a pedagogical concern with producing translations that went beyond surface-level accuracy, incorporating cultural and linguistic nuance to make the text feel authentic.

Grammatical translation followed as the third most preferred technique, receiving 223 responses or 16.18%. This technique emphasizes syntactic and structural correctness, maintaining grammatical alignment between the source and target texts. While not the most dominant approach among language teachers, its presence in the results highlights that a segment of educators still values formal linguistic precision and sentence-level accuracy. This may be particularly relevant in academic or formal translation tasks, where structural integrity and grammatical correctness are expected. Lastly, word-for-word translation is the least preferred technique, with only 140 responses or 10.16%. This technique involves translating each word exactly as it appeared in the original, often without regard for idiomatic usage, contextual flow, or grammatical structure in the target language. The low percentage suggests that most language teachers are cautious about relying on such a rigid method, possibly because it resulted in awkward or unnatural translations that fail to convey the intended meaning effectively. In teaching contexts, such literalness hindered students' understanding and misrepresented the functional use of language.

Overall, the data clearly show that communicative translation is the most preferred method among language teachers, reflecting a shift toward more dynamic, audience-centered translation practices. This finding is aligned with the study conducted by Karam & Smith (2020), which underscored that communicative translation is often favored in educational settings because it ensures that translations are not only accurate in content

but also culturally appropriate and easily understood by the target audience. Their research highlights how communicative translation enhances the effectiveness of instructional materials, fostered better learner.

Conclusions

Following data analysis, the present researchers reached the following findings:

In the overall results, word- for- word translation emerged as the most preferred type while communicative translation received the lowest rating. Among English Major students, word- for- word translation ranked highest while communicative translation was the least preferred. This result was unexpected, as idiomatic or communicative translation was often associated with natural language use, but it suggested that English majors may still have a

Transparency of literal translations. In the case of Filipino Major students, word- for- word translation was again the highest, and communicative translation was the lowest. This preference pattern indicated a stronger inclination toward structural fidelity and perhaps a deeper concern with preserving the grammatical and lexical elements of the source language. On the other hand, Language Teachers showed a different trend, preferring idiomatic translation the most and assigning the lowest rating to grammatical translation.

Based on the results of the study, it was clear that word- for- word translation emerged as the most preferred translation type overall, while communicative translation received the lowest rating across all sectors. This suggested that there was a strong preference for accuracy, transparency, and structural fidelity in translation. Among both English Major and Filipino Major students, word- for- word translation ranked the highest, indicating a strong inclination towards maintaining the exact structure and lexicon of the source text. These students seemed to prioritize correctness and clarity in their translations, likely due to their academic training, which emphasized precise linguistic and grammatical elements over naturalness in the target language. This preference for literal translations suggested that students may view communicative translation as less faithful to the original text and less accurate in preserving the structure and form. On the other hand, Language Teachers showed a stark contrast in their preferences. They favored idiomatic translation and assigned the lowest rating to grammatical translation. This preference highlighted their focus on naturalness and fluency in the translated text. For Language Teachers, conveying the meaning of the original text in a culturally and linguistically appropriate way seems to take precedence over maintaining the exact grammatical structure. This trend suggested that they were more concerned with the audience's understanding and the functional aspects of communication rather than strict adherence to grammatical rules.

Based on the findings, the study concluded that there was a clear distinction in translation preferences between students and language educators. The majority of students favored word- for- word translation techniques, indicating their preference for

literal and structurally faithful renderings of the source text. This reflected their developing language proficiency and a desire for accuracy in terms of form. On the other hand, language educators showed a strong preference for idiomatic translation, emphasizing the importance of natural expression, cultural relevance, and overall communicative effectiveness. These differing preferences highlighted how translation strategies were shaped by academic level, training, and professional perspective. While students prioritized structure and accuracy, educators focused on meaning and fluency. This suggested that translation was not a fixed process but a flexible practice influenced by the translator's background and purpose.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher formulated the following recommendations:

1. Students this study will help language students understand the value of translation techniques in creating accurate and meaningful translations. By learning how different strategies affect the meaning of texts, students can develop better thinking skills and improve their ability to analyze and interpret content. This deeper understanding will not only improve their translation skills but also enhance their reading and comprehension in multiple languages. The results of the study can be turned into helpful learning materials, such as exercises, examples, and guides, which can be used in translation courses to support students' learning.
2. Instructors in translation and language studies can use the findings of this research to improve their teaching methods. With clearer knowledge of how different translation techniques work, instructors can teach more effectively and give students real-life examples and practical exercises. The study's findings can help them design teaching tools such as bilingual glossaries, translation workbooks, mobile apps, and video materials that make learning more engaging and interactive. These resources will help students apply what they learn in real-world situations.
3. Schools educational institutions can benefit by using the research to build better translation programs. Schools can create or improve language and translation courses using the study as a guide. By offering materials like bilingual textbooks, interactive learning tools, and real translation tasks, schools can give students a richer learning experience. These programs will help students become more fluent in multiple languages and prepare them for future careers in translation, interpretation, or international communication. Promoting these skills also supports cultural awareness and global understanding.
4. Future Researchers the study opens doors for future researchers to explore new ideas and methods in translation. Researchers can build on the results to study how different strategies affect the way meaning is transferred from one language to another. This can lead to better models of translation competence and deeper insight into how people think and process language during translation. Future studies may also look into the use of

technology, the role of culture, and the impact of training on translation quality, all of which can help improve the field.

5. Curriculum Developers the findings of this study can guide policy makers and curriculum developers in designing effective translation and language programs. By incorporating evidence-based strategies and practical translation tools, they can promote multilingual education and support national goals for language proficiency and cross-cultural communication.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors affirm adherence to ethical standards and confirm that informed consent was properly secured, participants were given the right to withdraw at any stage, and their identities remained confidential. The study complied with data privacy regulations, ensured the safety and well-being of all respondents, and declared the absence of any conflicts of interest. The authors also guarantees hat plagiarism was avoided, interpretations of the data were free from bias, and the findings were utilized solely for academic purposes.

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